

Christian Appropriation of the Sinai From Paul to Late Antiquity

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ABSTRACT

Christian appropriation of the Biblical sites of the Sinai Peninsula began as soon as monks first visited the region in the mid-fourth century. Monks and pilgrims emphasized their claim to the Sinai by stressing the perceived sins and weakness of the Israelites during the Exodus. Chapter 10 of Paul's 1 Corinthians describes a metaphorical spiritual journey into the Sinai as a way for Christians to demonstrate their superiority over Jews. Travelers to the Sinai, such as Egeria, the Piacenza pilgrim, and Cosmas Indicopleustes, implicitly or explicitly used 1 Corinthians as a guide for their journeys. Depictions on the Madaba Map refer to the sinfulness of the Israelites, thus justifying Christian superiority. Finally, Jerome's writings claimed that Moses, Mount Sinai, and the Mosaic Law were products of Christ.

Keywords: Sinai, supersession, appropriation, Christianity, Judaism, Biblical.

In the late fourth century, Christian monks began to discover the solitude of the Sinai Peninsula. In search of spiritual experiences, pilgrims followed the Christian monks to the Sinai Peninsula, including notable figures, such as Egeria and the Piacenza pilgrim in the fourth and sixth centuries. These pilgrims sought both the living example of the holy monks for their daily renunciation of the material world and the opportunity to visit and see the holy places from the Exodus. In *Mirage of the Saracen*, I described how the monks identified these sites and used those associations to justify the displacement of the indigenous nomads from the area and how pilgrims played a crucial role in disseminating these identifications throughout the Christian World.ⁱ

My discussion, however, only briefly touched on how these Christian groups appropriated the Biblical locations of Sinai from Judaism. Just as Christians believed that their faith superseded the Jews regarding their scriptures, they also took over holy sites, such as Mount Sinai, and the memory and veneration of holy figures such as Moses.ⁱⁱ Though late antique and earlier Judaism did not identify a specific location as "Mount Sinai" and there was no tradition of Jewish pilgrimage to the Sinai, Christians did have to contend with the Jewish conception of the Sinai in the Exodus account.

Beginning with Paul and continuing into late antiquity, Christians viewed the Hebrew people as committing many sins against God during the Exodus. Paul first laid out a path to appropriate Sinai sites for Christianity in 1 Corinthians by emphasizing Israelite negative traits

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and their intransigence towards God during the Exodus. Later Christians, who visited or depicted the Sinai, employed 1 Corinthians as a resource to alienate the Jews from spiritual ownership of the Sinai and to prove the superiority of the Christian faith. Visitors to the Sinai, such as Egeria, the Piacenza pilgrim, and Cosmas Indicopleustes, all described the sinful nature of the early Israelites during their journey through the Sinai or demonstrated that Christians could surpass the Israelites in righteousness by obeying God's will there. There are only a few remaining visual depictions of the Sinai Peninsula from the late antique period. One of those is the Madaba Map, which clearly indicates that the Hebrew people repeatedly sinned against God in the Sinai. By attending church and viewing the Map, Christians reinforced their claims to the Sinai. Whenever Christian monks lived a righteous life, pilgrims refrained from sin, or churchgoers observed evidence of Hebrew sinfulness, Christians asserted their spiritual ownership of the Sinai. Jerome took supersession even further.

By linking Mount Sinai from the Exodus with the town Pharan in the late antique Sinai, Jerome argued that the Mosaic Law was created by Jesus, thus depriving the Hebrew people of any connection with the Sinai. Just as Paul described how Christians could be superior to the Hebrews in holiness, Jerome demonstrated how Jesus and Christianity superseded Judaism itself.

The Sinai in 1 Corinthians

In 1 Corinthians, Paul uses the Exodus to extol Christians as the true inheritors of Israel, enhancing the importance of the Exodus account and the Sinai Peninsula for Christians.ⁱⁱⁱ Though originally written as a metaphor, Chapter 10 could be read as a template for reenacting the Exodus to prove the superiority of the Christian faith and its followers. Later Christian pilgrims to the Sinai seem to have interpreted Paul literally and used this chapter to reenact Christian superiority over Judaism.

Paul opens the chapter by referencing the spiritual guidance provided to the adherents of Christian doctrine who “were all under the cloud, and all passed through the sea”, through which the Israelites became baptized.^{iv} Paul is undoubtedly alluding to the splitting of the Red Sea and the “protective covering of the clouds” mentioned in Exodus 14:20.^v Next, Paul describes how the Israelites partook of spiritual sustenance through consuming *manna* and drink. The water emanated from the Rock of Sinai, which Paul identified as “Christ” thereby reshaping the Exodus into a proto-Christian expedition.^{vi} It is conceivable that Paul perceived this as a “prototype of the Lord's Supper” or merely a precursor to the observance of the Eucharist, further prefiguring Christian beliefs and practices.^{vii} Paul proceeds to delineate the failings of the Israelites, who grumbled about their desert sojourn, coveted malevolent desires, engaged in idolatry, and committed acts of fornication.^{viii} He concludes by stating, “these things happened to them to serve as an example, and they were recorded to instruct us, upon whom the culmination of the ages has arrived.”^{ix}

1 Corinthians and visitors to the Sinai

Paul's discourse of these events from the Exodus, originally intended as a spiritual guide, might have been used by pilgrims and monks in the Sinai as an instructive manual. Each of Paul's observations could be “reenacted” by pilgrims during their journey to the Sinai. Monks and pilgrims could visit the crossing point of the Red Sea, position themselves beneath the clouds of Sinai, partake of *manna*, and be compelled to drink from the springs of Sinai. In the sixth century, Cosmas Indicopleustes interpreted his voyage to Sinai in this manner, as evidenced by his correlation of the contemporary fountain at Pharan with the “Rock of Christ” mentioned by Paul.^x

The pilgrims and monks could also steer clear of the transgressions committed by the Israelites by accepting the barren nature of the Sinai, refraining from voicing complaints about their circumstances, and venerating the one true God rather than a Golden Calf. Through this approach, Christian monks and pilgrims could demonstrate their spiritual superiority over both the ancient Hebrew people and the contemporaneous Jews. Just as in Jerusalem, where the evolution of liturgy and rituals connected to the suffering of Christ aided in consecrating the sacred sites, a similar reenactment of the Exodus through rituals could empower Christians to lay claim to Sinai as their own “holy mountain of God.”

Although Egeria does not explicitly pass judgment on the failures of the Israelites in her travelogue, she does reference the Israelites’ deviation from monotheism and implies that they were unworthy of the holy sites in Sinai. Conversely, Egeria and the monks are portrayed as deserving of Mount Sinai.^{xi} While Egeria doesn’t directly cite Paul’s *Letter to the Corinthians* which criticizes the Israelites for their lust, idolatry, and fornication in Sinai, she does bring up the graves of those who lusted and perished due to a plague, an observation she made in the valley beneath Mount Sinai.^{xii} By indirectly mentioning the “sins” of the Israelites, her account implies that the Christians were able to claim the Sinai because the ancient Israelites had strayed from the path of the Lord, with the Christians now surpassing them in sanctity. She implicitly follows Paul’s instructions by avoiding these transgressions.

In the valley nestled between Mount Sinai and Mount Choreb, the Piacenza pilgrim described how water (or dew) descended from the sky, which the monks referred to as *manna*. These monks collected the *manna* and provided it to pilgrims in *ampullae* as benedictions.^{xiii} While Egeria mistakenly attributed this event to the Bible occurring around Mount Sinai (which was not accurate), the Piacenza pilgrim describes it as a phenomenon of the sixth century. This distinction allowed the Piacenza pilgrim to fulfill one of the examples outlined in Paul’s 1 Corinthians by experiencing the taste of the *manna*.^{xiv} The notion that *manna* could be gathered by the monks in the sixth century creates a profound impression that the monks were participants in the Exodus, replacing the Jews in the holy landscape of Sinai.

Representations of Sinai on the Madaba Map

An important pictorial representation of the Sinai Peninsula appears on the Madaba Map, a religious document discovered in the remains of a sixth-century church in modern-day Madaba, Jordan.^{xv} (refer to Figure 1). Regrettably, for our intended purposes, the section of the Madaba Map which depicts the Sinai has sustained damage, yet three inscriptions remain discernible. None of these three annotations are associated with specific locations, although one pertains to Raphidim, while the other two describe the desert. (Refer to Figure 2). The positioning of Mount Sinai falls within the part of the map that has not been preserved. Regardless, the surviving fragments of the map indicate that the Sinai’s Biblical associations would likely have been prominently highlighted, even considering Madaba’s geographical distance from Sinai. The map itself demonstrates what would have constituted common standard knowledge about the Sinai within the nearby regions.

The Madaba Map includes two inscriptions that link the Sinai desert with the Israelites and events from the Bible. A partially damaged inscription in what would have been the northern part of the Sinai desert reads, ἔρημος ἐνθα] τὸς Ἰσραηλίτας ἔ[σ]ω[σ]ιν ὁ χαλκοῦς ὄφις,^{xvi} referencing the “Serpent of Brass”. This serpent was fashioned by Moses to rescue his people from snakebites inflicted by God.^{xvii} This inscription not only underscores Moses’s ability to protect his people, but also highlights the transgressions of the Israelites who began doubting God and their own survival. The second inscription appears along the western shore of the Sinai Peninsula and stands

out as one of the few descriptions on the map written in red tesserae. It clearly associates the western Sinai desert with the desert of Sin and reads *ἔρημος Σιν ὅπου κατεπέμφθη τὸ μάννα καὶ ἡ ὄρνυγομήτρα*.^{xviii} In this context, the desert of Sin appears as the location for both suffering and the questioning of God. However, it was also the place where God sent manna and quails to nourish the Israelites. Both inscriptions explicitly refer to the Israelites' propensity for and their inclination to question God's wisdom. In one instance, God sent serpents to attack the Israelites, but He then instructed Moses on how to save the sinners. In the other case, the people complained to God about their hunger, but He saved them without retribution. These two legends suggest that the mosaic may have been influenced by Paul's 1 Corinthians, as each inscription underscores the Israelites' tendency to doubt thereby accentuating the "superior" moral stance of the Christians who did not complain or sin. Consequently, whenever someone attended the church and beheld the Madaba Map, it would have further fortified the Christian claim to the Holy Land as a whole and the Sinai Peninsula in particular.

In his commentary on the minor prophet Habakkuk, the writer Jerome of the later fourth century describes how Jesus gave the laws to Moses on Mount Sinai. He explains, "Because Bethlehem is situated towards the south, in which the Lord and Savior was born, so there it is said of him, 'The Lord will come from the south'; that is, he will be born in Bethlehem, whence he shall rise. And since he, who was born in Bethlehem, also gave the former law on Mount Sinai, he also is 'holy who comes from Mount Pharan,' since Pharan is in the area of Mount Sinai".^{xix} In constructing this torturous and tenuous connection, Jerome attempts to appropriate the *entire* Jewish Law, the figure of Moses, and the events that transpired in Sinai into the domain of Christianity. Moses is ignored and replaced by Jesus as the lawgiver on the mountain. Consequently, Mount Sinai takes on the role of the place where Jesus first contacted the world and interacted with the Jewish people. Jesus created the Covenant and the Jewish Law; thus, he possesses the authority to both fulfill and modify the law. This interpretation also allows the Christians to appropriate the Sinai Peninsula. By associating Mount Sinai with Mount Pharan, Jerome establishes a link between events from the Bible and an actual location in the Sinai Desert – the town of Pharan. He makes a point that this town is situated within the vicinity of Mount Sinai. Jerome's interpretation reshaped the significance of one of the most important foundations of Judaism into the earliest manifestation of Jesus' influence and supremacy.

Jerome, however, never personally visited Sinai. His theological interpretations remained in the realm of the mind. Yet, others were driven by a desire to experience the Sinai firsthand, seeking to connect the tangible world with the Bible in innovative ways. For example, Cosmas Indicopleustes embarked on a journey that fortified his belief in the superiority of the Christian message. He believed that the Sinai desert stood as a constant reminder of the truth of the gospels for all people, especially for those who doubted. The proof, in his view, was the enigmatic inscriptions on numerous rocks scattered throughout the desert, which he believed were the inscriptions of the wandering Israelites.^{xx}

Cosmas, like the other pilgrims and the Madaba Map, internalized Paul's pronouncements in 1 Corinthians, projecting New Testament concepts onto the locations of the Exodus. As argued by Cyril of Jerusalem, the fact that the locations of the Sinai existed, was proof that the Exodus account was true.^{xxi} The locations of the Bible were inhabited with Christians who substantiated their superior claim to the Sinai through their devout ways of life. Any assertions made by the Jewish community were dismissed, as their rejection of God during the Exodus and of Jesus in the present invalidated their claims.

REFERENCES

ⁱ Ward 2014.

ⁱⁱ The literature on this topic is extensive and cannot be fully described here. See Dunn 2000, pp. 248-254; Hirshman 1996; Mac Cormack, S. 1990, pp. 7-40.

ⁱⁱⁱ Goppelt 1982, pp. 140-151.

^{iv} Cf. NRSV 1 Cor. 10:1-2: *Ὁὐ θέλω γὰρ ὑμᾶς ἀγνοεῖν, ἀδελφοί, ὅτι οἱ πατέρες ἡμῶν πάντες ὑπὸ τὴν νεφέλῃν ἦσαν, καὶ πάντες διὰ τῆς θαλάσσης διήθλον, καὶ πάντες εἰς τὸν Μωσῆν ἐβαπτίσαντο ἐν τῇ νεφέλῃ καὶ ἐν τῇ θαλάσσει...* See Ferguson 2009, pp. 151-152.

^v Goppelt 1982, pp. 144-145.

^{vi} Cf. 1 Cor. 10:3-4: *καὶ πάντες τὸ αὐτὸ βρῶμα πνευματικὸν ἔφαγον, καὶ πάντες τὸ αὐτὸ πόμα πνευματικὸν ἔπιον· ἔπιον γὰρ ἐκ πνευματικῆς ἀκολουθούσης πέτρας, ἣ δὲ πέτρα ἦν ὁ Χριστός.*

^{vii} Goppelt 1982, p. 145.

^{viii} Cf. 1 Cor. 10:5-10: *ἀλλ' οὐκ ἐν τοῖς πλείοσιν αὐτῶν εὐδόκησεν ὁ θεός· κατεστρώθησαν γὰρ ἐν τῇ ἐρήμῳ. Ταῦτα δὲ τυποὶ ἡμῶν ἐγενήθησαν, εἰς τὸ μὴ εἶναι ἡμᾶς ἐπιθυμητὰς κακῶν, καθὼς κάκεῖνοι ἐπεθύμησαν. Μηδὲ εἰδωλόλατραι γίνεσθε, καθὼς τινες αὐτῶν ὥσπερ γέγραπται, Ἐκάθισεν ὁ λαὸς φαγεῖν καὶ πιεῖν, καὶ ἀνέστησαν παίξιν. Μηδὲ πορνεύωμεν, καθὼς τινες αὐτῶν ἐπόρνυσαν, καὶ ἔπεσον ἐν μιᾷ ἡμέρᾳ εἰκοσιτρεῖς χιλιάδες. Μηδὲ ἐκπειράζωμεν τὸν Κύριον, καθὼς τινες αὐτῶν ἐπείρασαν, καὶ ὑπὸ τῶν ὄψεων ἀπόλλυντο. Μηδὲ γογγύετε, καθάπερ τινὲς αὐτῶν ἐγόγγυσαν, καὶ ἀπόλλυντο ὑπὸ τοῦ ὄλοθρευτοῦ.*

^{ix} Cf. NRSV 1 Cor. 10:11: *ταῦτα δὲ τυπικῶς συνέβαινον ἐκείνοις· ἐγγράφη δὲ πρὸς νοθεσίαν ἡμῶν, εἰς οὓς τὰ τέλη τῶν αἰῶνων κατήνηκεν.*

^x Cosmas Indicopleustes. *Christian Topography*. 17 (*Sources Chrétiennes* 141).

^{xi} Egeria. *Itinerarium*. 2.2, 3.4 (CCSL 175), *senex integer et monachus a prima uita et, ut hic dicunt, ascites, et ... qualis dignus est esse in eo loco.*

^{xii} Numbers 11.34; Egeria 5.10, *vidimus etiam in extrema iam ualle ipsa memorias concupiscentiae, in eo tamen loco, in quo denuo reuersi sumus ad iter nostrum ...*

^{xiii} Piacenza Pilgrim. *Itinerarium*. 39 (CCSL 175), *inter Sina et Choreb est uallis, in qua certis temporibus descendit ros de caelo, quem manna appellant et coagulatur et fit tamquam granum masticis et collegitur et doleos exinde plenos habent in monasterio, unde et benedictionem dant ampullas modicas. Nam et nobis inde dederunt sextaria quinque. Ex quo etiam pro condito bibent et novis dederunt et bibimus.*

^{xiv} Cf. 1 Corinthians 10:3.

^{xv} See Donner 1999; Meimaris 1999; The sources of the map include Eusebius' *Onomasticon*, the Peutinger Table, and the *Itinerarium* of the Piacenza pilgrim, but the most important source was the Septuagint, see Di Segni 1999.

^{xvi} Donner 1999, p. 43 no. 21; Alliata 1999, p. 95 no. 135.

^{xvii} Cf. Numbers 21.5-9.

^{xviii} Donner 1999, p. 69-70 no. 97; Alliata 1999, p. 95, no. 137.

^{xix} Jerome writes *Deus ab austro ueniet, et sanctus de monte Pharan*. The original Hebrew text says *יְהוָה בָּא מִתַּמָּן הַקֹּדֶשׁ מִתַּמָּן יְהוָה* which is translated by the NRSV as, "God came from Taman, the holy one from Mount Paran" (Hab. 3:3). The LXX translates, *ὁ θεὸς ἐκ Θαμῶν ἦξει, καὶ ὁ ἅγιος ἐξ ὄρους κατασκίου δασέος*, "God came from Taiman, and the Holy One from the mountain of the shadowy wilderness" (Jerome translates this as "et sanctus de monte umbroso et condense"). Jerome's use of the Hebrew text differs significantly from the Septuagint translation and allows him to create a connection between Mount Sinai and Jesus. His use of the Hebrew TMN translated as *auster* is in accordance with Hebrew usage, but the Septuagint translators clearly thought that the text indicated the place Taman and that the word was not used in the directional sense. By translating TMN as *auster*, Jerome can connect Jesus to biblical prophecy because he came from the south, not from Taman, and then can connect Jesus to the Law at Mount Sinai. Jerome defends his interpretation by suggesting that the Hebrew Scriptures define Pharan as "the mountain of the shadowy wilderness" Cf. Jerome. *Commentarius in Abacuc*. 2.3.3 (CCL 76A:623), *[s]ed quia pro monte umbroso et condense, in Hebraeo scriptum est mons Pharan, et Pharan interpretatur os uidentis.*

^{xx} Cosmas Indicopleustes. *Ibid.* 5.53-4: *Λαβόντες δὲ καὶ παρὰ Θεοῦ τὸν νόμον ἐγγράφως καὶ διδασκόμενοι γράμματα νεοστί, καὶ ὥσπερ παιδευτηρίῳ ἡσυχῶ τῇ ἐρήμῳ χρησάμενος ὁ Θεὸς*

τεσσαράκοντα ἔτη εἶασεν αὐτοὺς καταλαξεῦσαι τὰ γράμματα. Ὅθεν ἔστιν ἰδεῖν ἐν ἐκείνῃ τῇ ἐρήμῳ, λέγω δὴ τοῦ Σιναΐου ὄρους, ἐν πάσαις ταῖς καταπαύσεσι πάντας τοὺς λίθους τῶν αὐτόθι, τοὺς ἐκ τῶν ὀρέων ἀποκλωμένους, γεγραμμένους γράμμασι γλυπτοῖς ἑβραϊκοῖς, ὡς αὐτὸς ἐγὼ πεζεύσας τοὺς τόπους μαρτυρῶ. Ἄτινα καὶ τινες Ἰουδαῖοι ἀναγνόντες διηγοῦντο ἡμῖν λέγοντες γεγράφθαι οὕτως: Ἄπαρσις τοῦδε, ἐκ φυλῆς τῆσδε, ἔτει τῷδε, μηνὶ τῷδε, καθὰ καὶ παρ' ἡμῖν πολλάκις τινὲς ἐν ταῖς ξενίαις γράφουσιν. Αὐτοὶ δὲ καί, ὡς νεωστὶ μαθόντες γράμματα, συνεχῶς ἄτε χρῶντο καὶ ἐπλήθυνον γράφοντες, ὥστε πάντας τοὺς τόπους ἐκείνους μεσοτὺς εἶναι γραμμάτων ἑβραϊκῶν γλυπτῶν εἰσέτι καὶ νῦν σφριζομένων διὰ τοὺς ἀπίστους, ὡς ἔγωγε οἶμαι. Ἐξὸν δὲ τῷ βουλομένῳ ἐν τοῖς τόποις γενέσθαι καὶ θεάσασθαι, ἤγουν ἐρωτήσαι καὶ μαθεῖν περὶ τούτου ὡς ἀλήθειαν εἶπαμεν. Πρώτως οὖν Ἑβραῖοι παρὰ τοῦ Θεοῦ σοφισθέντες καὶ γράμματα διὰ τῶν λιθίνων πλακῶν ἐκείνων παραλαβόντες καὶ μεμαθηκότες τεσσαράκοντα ἔτη ἐν τῇ ἐρήμῳ γεινιῶσι τοῖς Φοῖνιξί παραδεδώκασι κατ' ἐκεῖνο καιροῦ, πρώτῳ Κάδμῳ τῷ Τυρίῳ βασιλεῖ, ἐξ ἐκείνου παρέλαβον Ἕλληνας, λοιπὸν καθεξῆς πάντα τὰ ἔθνη.

^{xxi} Cyril of Jerusalem. *Catecheses ad Illuminados*, ed. W. Reischl and J. Rupp 1848–60. (Munich: Lentner, 1848-60 [Reprint, Hildesheim: Olms, 1967]), 4.10: *Οὗτος ἐσταυρώθη ὑπὲρ τῶν ἀμαρτιῶν ἡμῶν ἀληθῶς. Κἂν γὰρ ἀρνήσασθαι βουληθῆς, ὁ τόπος ἐλέγχει σε φαινόμενος, ὁ μακάριος οὗτος Γολγοθᾶς, ἐν ᾧ νῦν, διὰ τὸν ἐν αὐτῷ σταυρωθέντα, συγκεκροτήμεθα. Καὶ τοῦ ζύλου τοῦ σταυροῦ πᾶσα λοιπὸν ἡ οἰκουμένη κατὰ μέρος ἐπληρώθη.* On Cyril, see Drijvers 2004.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Alliaia, E. (1999). The Legends of the Madaba Map. In: M. Piccirillo and E. Alliaia, eds. *The Madaba Map centenary 1897-1997: Travelling through the Byzantine Umayyad Period*. Volume 135: Studium Biblicum Franciscanum. Jerusalem, pp. 47-102, 95.
2. Di Segni, L. (1999). The “Onomasticon” of Eusebius and the Madaba Map. In: M. Piccirillo and E. Alliaia, eds. *The Madaba Map centenary 1897-1997: Travelling through the Byzantine Umayyad Period*. Studium Biblicum Franciscanum. Jerusalem, pp. 115-20.
3. Donner, H. (1992). *The mosaic map of Madaba: An introductory guide*. Kampen: Kok Pharos Publishing House.
4. Drijvers, J. (2004). *Cyril of Jerusalem: Bishop and city*. Leiden: Brill.
5. Dunn, M. (2000). *The emergence of monasticism: From the Desert Fathers to the Early Middle Ages*. Oxford: Blackwell.
6. Ferguson, E. (2009). *Baptism in the early Church: History, theology, and liturgy in the first five centuries*. Grand Rapids, Michigan/Cambridge, U.K.: Eerdmans.
7. Goppelt, L. (1982). Typos: *The typological interpretation of the Old Testament in the New*. Translated by Donald H. Madvig. Grand Rapids, Michigan/Cambridge, U.K.: Eerdmans.
8. Hirshman, M. (1996). *A Rivalry of Genius: Jewish and Christian biblical interpretation in late antiquity*. Albany: State University of New York Press.
9. MacCormack, S. (1990). The organization of sacred topography. In: R. Ousterhout, ed. *The Blessings of Pilgrimage*. Urbana: University of Illinois Press, pp. 7–40.
10. Meimaris, Y. (1999). The discovery of the Madaba Map. In: Piccirillo, M., and E. Alliaia ed. (1999). *The Madaba Map centenary 1897-1997: Travelling through the Byzantine Umayyad period*. Jerusalem: Studium Biblicum Franciscanum. pp. 25-36.
11. Piccirillo, M., and E. Alliaia ed. (1999). *The Madaba Map centenary 1897-1997: Travelling through the Byzantine Umayyad period*. Jerusalem: Studium Biblicum Franciscanum.
12. Ward, W. (2014). *Mirage of the Saracen: Christians and nomads in the Sinai Peninsula in late antiquity*. Oakland: University of California Press.